

Bayesian building count estimation using ground surveys and satellite-derived data

Gianluca Boo^{*1}, Heather R. Chamberlain¹ and Andrew J. Tatem¹

¹WorldPop, University of Southampton, University Rd, SO17 1BJ Southampton, UK

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Summary

This study integrates ground surveys with satellite-derived datasets in a Bayesian hierarchical model to improve the accuracy of gridded building count data in Kasai-Oriental, Democratic Republic of the Congo. Ground surveys enumerated freestanding structures in 213 small areas, which were fit using gridded building count from satellite-derived building footprints according to different settlement classes. The model substantially reduced bias, inaccuracy, and imprecision compared to the original building footprint data. Posterior estimates consisted of probabilistic gridded building count for the entire province. The study highlights the benefits of Bayesian assessments of satellite-derived datasets in data-scarce contexts.

KEYWORDS: Bayesian Hierarchical Models, Satellite Imagery, Building Footprints, Ground Surveys, Gridded Building Counts

1 Introduction

Bayesian high-resolution population estimates are becoming increasingly popular in data-scarce settings because of their ability to address the lack of actionable national census data (Leasure et al., 2020). These estimates rely on accurate household surveys and geospatial datasets, particularly building footprint data extracted from satellite imagery (Boo et al., 2022). However, inconsistencies among data providers and limited ground-truth validations underscore potential unreliability issues (Chamberlain et al., 2024). These issues are particularly critical in the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC), where forest, smoke, and cloud coverage typically impact accurate building footprint extraction. Our study tackles these issues by integrating building footprint data with ground surveys in a Bayesian hierarchical model to estimate building counts at high spatial resolution in the sparsely settled Kasai-Oriental province.

*gianluca.boo@soton.ac.uk

2 Data and Methods

2.1 Data

We accessed ground surveys recording the number of permanent freestanding structures across 213 small areas, referred to as “clusters”, between March and April 2021 (Flowminder Foundation et al., 2021). While the primary goal of these surveys was to enumerate the residents of each cluster, ancillary data on building use and characteristics were systematically collected. We also accessed gridded building count at a spatial resolution of approximately 100 m produced from building footprint data derived from satellite imagery and other sources in 2024 (CIESIN, 2024). In addition, we derived urban, peri-urban, and rural settlement classes from the 2023 Global Human Settlement Model Grid (GHS-SMOD) (Schiavina, Melchiorri, and Pesaresi, 2023). The gridded datasets were summarised within the cluster boundaries using a coverage-based weighted sum for gridded building count and the mode for settlement classes. Figure 1 shows the location of the ground surveys carried out in Kasai-Oriental alongside gridded building count derived from building footprint data, with a zoomed-in view of a selected two selected clusters highlighting the surveyed buildings.

2.2 Bayesian Hierarchical Model

Our model adopted a hierarchical structure consistent with existing frameworks for high-resolution population estimation (Boo et al., 2022). Equation 1 models the B_i observed building count from ground surveys across the i clusters as a Poisson process, with the \hat{B}_i expected building count expressed on a logarithmic scale.

$$B_i \sim \text{Poisson}(\hat{B}_i) \quad (1)$$

Equation 2 models \hat{B}_i as a log-normal process to account for over-dispersion, with mean μ_i and variance σ_s specific to settlement class s —urban, peri-urban, and rural—capturing different built-up contexts.

$$\hat{B}_i \sim \text{logN}(\mu_i, \sigma_s) \quad (2)$$

Lastly, Equation 3 models μ_i using a linear regression with s -specific intercept terms α_s , a covariate X_i representing centred and scaled log-transformed building count from building footprint data, and s -specific random effects β_s .

$$\mu_i = \alpha_s + X_i \cdot \beta_s \quad (3)$$

We implemented the model in Stan (2.32.2) (Stan Development Team, 2021) using three Markov chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) chains, each with 5,000 iterations. We assessed goodness-of-fit for in-sample and out-of-sample posterior estimates using the following metrics: 1) bias (the mean of residuals), 2) imprecision (the standard deviation of residuals), 3) inaccuracy (the mean of absolute residuals), 4) R^2 (the squared Pearson correlation coefficient of residuals), 5) root mean squared error (RMSE) (square root of the average squared differences between estimated and observed values), and 6) credible intervals (CIs) coverage (percentage of observations within the 95% CIs) (Gelman et al., 2014). Posterior building count estimates were derived for grid cells of approximately 100

Figure 1: Ground surveys location and gridded building count from building footprints across Kasai-Oriental with a close-up view of a selected urban (A) and rural (B) cluster with surveyed buildings.

m using the model parameters and gridded datasets available for the province together with a comparative measure of model uncertainty—the difference between the posterior upper and lower 95% CIs divided by the mean estimate. Input data, scripts, and results are publicly available in an open-access repository (Boo et al., 2025).

3 Results

Figure 2 compares building counts from ground surveys with building footprint counts and mean posterior estimates with 95% CIs. The figure shows that building footprint data produced frequent overestimation, while the mean posterior estimates provided a closer approximation of the ground truth. In clusters featuring over 125 buildings, building footprint data and mean posteriors underestimated building count because of limited building footprint coverage. However, posterior estimates successfully captured the variability in surveyed building count within the 95% CIs.

Figure 2: Building count from ground surveys versus building count from building footprints (left) and mean building count in-sample posterior estimates with CIs (right). The diagonal dashed black lines represent one-to-one relationships.

Table 1 summarises goodness-of-fit metrics for building count from building footprints and posterior estimates. The results confirm the findings from Figure 2, where bias, imprecision, and inaccuracy were systematically lower for the mean posterior estimates compared with the building footprint counts. In particular, the mean posterior estimates overestimated ground surveys by an average of 1.10 units, compared with 4.95 units for building footprint counts. This enhanced goodness-of-fit is confirmed by an improved R^2 value and a RMSE reduction. Notably, 95.77% of the surveyed building count fell within the 95% CIs, demonstrating robustness.

Table 1: Goodness-of-fit metrics for building count derived from building footprints and in-sample mean posteriors.

	Building footprints	Mean posteriors
Bias	-4.95	-1.10
Imprecision	29.79	27.66
Inaccuracy	21.90	19.62
R^2	0.51	0.52
RMSE	30.13	27.62
CIs coverage		95.77%

Figure 3 shows the gridded mean posterior estimates (left) and corresponding uncertainty levels (right) at a spatial resolution of approximately 100 m across Kasai-Oriental. The mean posterior estimates closely align with the patterns observed in gridded building count derived from building footprints. The highest estimates are concentrated in the central city of Mbuji-Mayi and settlements along the main road network. In contrast, most of the province comprises sparsely populated rural areas, with building count typically ranging from 2 to 20. Model uncertainty mirrors these settlement patterns, reflecting the hierarchical model structure based on settlement class, where urban areas exhibit reduced uncertainty compared to rural areas, featuring uncertainty levels peaking at 375%.

Figure 3: Gridded posterior estimates with mean building count (left) and uncertainty levels (right) across Kasai-Oriental.

4 Discussion

This study addressed persisting reliability issues in building footprint data derived from satellite imagery by combining them with ground surveys. Our Bayesian hierarchical model demonstrated that building footprint data alone offered a limited approximation of the ground truth, among others, because of known issues affecting satellite imagery (Chamberlain et al., 2024). By leveraging a hierarchical structure based on three settlement classes, the model provided an improved representation of building count in the surveyed clusters. Crucially, the results offered unprecedented probabilistic insights into the limitations of satellite-derived building footprint data, especially in rural areas where coverage was less consistent than in urban areas. These results emphasise the importance of considering ground truth and contextual factors when working with satellite-derived data to assess urban development, identify disaster-prone areas, and map population distributions. This framework for improved estimation of building count distribution was successfully embedded in an existing Bayesian model for gridded population estimation in the same province, where a more comprehensive analysis of the results is provided (Boo et al., 2025).

5 References

- Boo G, Darin E, Leasure DR, et al. (2022). High-resolution population estimation using household survey data and building footprints. *Nature Communications*, 13(1), 1330.
- Boo G, Darin E, Chamberlain HR et al. (2025). Tackling public health data gaps through Bayesian high-resolution population estimation: a case study of Kasai-Oriental, Democratic Republic of the Congo [preprint, version 1]. *VeriXiv*, 2:8.
- Chamberlain HR, Darin E, Adewole WA, et al. (2024). Building footprint data for countries in Africa: to what extent are existing data products comparable? *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems*, 110, 102104.
- Center for Integrated Earth System Information (CIESIN) (2024). *GRID3 COD - Settlement Extents, Version 3.1*. New York, US: Grid3. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.7916/d6gy-yh28>.
- Flowminder Foundation, École de Santé Publique de Kinshasa, University of Southampton, et al. (2021). *Microcensus in the provinces of Haut-Katanga, Haut-Lomami, Ituri, Kasai, Kasai-Oriental, Lomami and Sud-Kivu (Democratic Republic of the Congo), Version 2.2*.
- Gelman A, Carlin JB, Stern HS, et al. (2014). *Bayesian Data Analysis*. 3rd ed. CRC Press, Boca Raton.
- Leasure DR, Jochem WC, Weber EM, et al. (2020). National population mapping from sparse survey data: A hierarchical Bayesian modeling framework to account for uncertainty. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 117(39), 24173–24179.
- Schiavina M, Melchiorri M and Pesaresi M (2023). *GHS-SMOD R2023A - GHS settlement layers, application of the Degree of Urbanisation methodology (stage I) to GHS-POP R2023A and GHS-BUILT-S R2023A, multitemporal (1975-2030)*. European Commission, Joint Research Centre (JRC), Ispra, Italy.

Stan Development Team (2021). *Stan modeling language users guide and reference manual, Version 2.28*. Available at: <https://mc-stan.org>.

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Biographies

Gianluca Boo is a Senior Research Fellow at the University of Southampton building Bayesian modelling pipelines for high-resolution population mapping and estimation. His work focuses on developing bespoke Bayesian statistical models integrating demographic and geospatial data. He collaborates with national and international partners to foster data-driven decision-making.

Heather Chamberlain is a Senior Enterprise Fellow at the University of Southampton. Her work focuses on integrating geospatial data and quantitative methods for high-resolution mapping of populations, sociodemographics, and health. Most recently, this has been through the GRID3 project, collaborating with partners in Zambia and the Democratic Republic of Congo.

Andrew J. Tatem is a Professor and Founder of WorldPop at the University of Southampton specialising in mapping populations and their dynamics, particularly in low- and middle-income countries. His interests include demographic and geospatial data for disease, disaster, and development applications, leading impactful global collaborations.